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before transplanting. N was applied as per treatment (Table 1).

Sesbania alone in 1989 and 1990 produced more than 6 t grain/ha (about 2.5 t more than the control), which was statistically equal to 120 kg N/ha as prilled urea (PU) (Table 2). In 1991, *S. rostrata* alone (16 t green biomass = 56 kg N) was significantly superior to PU. Initially in 1988, *Sesbania* alone could contribute to producing rice yield equal to only 90 kg N/ha. But response to GM increased with time, probably due to the buildup of organic matter. *S. rostrata* with PU and FYM + PU produced yields significantly higher than the urea split in 1991 (Table 2). Initially in 1988 and 1989, GM (both *S. rostrata* and *S. aculeata*) had some superiority over PU, but in 1990, the differences were nonsignificant.

These findings indicated that *Sesbania* GM alone was capable of producing and sustaining more than a 6 t/ha rice yield, equal to more than 100 kg inorganic N. Green manuring with about 60 kg fertilizer N boosted rice yield to 6.8 t/ha.

Economic analysis revealed that using FYM increased the cultivation cost by US\$15 and GM by US\$27.20, but this was compensated by their yield increases. Integrating organic sources with organic N economized fertilizer N by 50% with GM and 42% with FYM. GM + PU and FYM + PU gave an extra benefit of US\$36 and US\$24 over the recommended dose of 120 kg N. GM alone gave an extra benefit of US\$260/ha over no N and US\$30/ha over 90 kg of urea N. These findings are useful for poor and marginal farmers who possess little purchasing power. ■

Crop management

Managing rice nurseries during winter season in the Hill Zone, Karnataka, India

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The Hill Zone of Karnataka, India, is situated between 11°56' and 14°39' N, 74°38' and 76°4' E. Because low temperatures prevail during the winter season (21-25 °C maximum and 7-13 °C minimum temperatures between 1st wk of December and 3rd wk of January), it

takes 60-65 d for rice seedlings to attain an acceptable minimum height of 15 cm for transplanting. This slow growth and development delays transplanting, and harvesting may not be completed before the onset of monsoon.

Multilocation field experiments were conducted during 1992-93 winter months at RRS, Mudigere, Agricultural Research Station, Mudigere, and Agricultural Research Station, Ponnampet, with the objective to determine suitable methods for raising healthy, vigorous rice seedlings within 25-30 d.

Each experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four

Table 1. Air and soil temperature (°C) as influenced by different treatments in winter rice nurseries.^a Hill Zone, Karnataka, India, 1992-93.

Treatment	Air temperature near plant zone (°C)			Soil temperature near root zone (°C)		
	1992	1993	Mean ^b	1992	1993	Mean ^b
<i>Raised bed</i>						
Control	19.8	20.5	20.1	18.1	20.0	19.0
Rice straw	16.1	22.0	19.0	12.5	15.7	14.1
Polythene	32.1	31.2	31.6	26.1	24.3	25.2
Double P	20.1	22.5	21.3	26.6	23.7	23.1
<i>Flat bed</i>						
Control	20.1	21.6	20.8	20.4	22.1	21.2
Rice straw	17.6	21.0	19.3	13.6	17.2	15.4
Polythene	33.1	32.5	32.8	25.8	25.2	25.5
Double P	21.8	21.6	21.7	22.1	22.7	22.4
Mean	22.5	23.3	-	20.2	21.3	-
LSD 0.05	1.3	1.4		1.4	1.5	

^aValues presented are the average for 15 d after sowing at 5 cm above and 5 cm below the soil surface. ^bMean of 3 sites.

Table 2. Seedling dry weight (g/seedling) and height (cm) at 25 d after sowing as influenced by different treatments in management of rice nurseries during the winter. Hill Zone, Karnataka, India, 1992-93.

Treatment	Seedling dry weight			Seedling height		
	1992	1993	Mean ^a	1992	1993	Mean ^b
<i>Raised bed</i>						
Control	0.276	0.279	0.277	10.10	9.12	9.61
Rice straw	0.080	0.055	0.067	0.52	0.59	0.55
Polythene	0.974	1.101	1.037	17.83	19.13	18.45
Double P	0.768	0.730	0.749	12.86	13.48	13.17
<i>Flat bed</i>						
Control	0.307	0.270	0.288	9.82	8.90	9.36
Rice straw	0.042	0.034	0.038	0.78	0.42	0.60
Polythene	0.935	0.971	0.953	20.52	20.71	20.16
Double P	0.720	0.703	0.711	17.21	17.91	17.56
LSD (0.05)	0.245	0.256		0.97	1.63	

^aMean of 3 sites.

replications. At each site, the recommended doses of farmyard manure (5 kg/m²) and inorganic fertilizer (90-45-45 g NPK/m²) were applied before sowing. Pregerminated seeds of three varieties (IET6893, CTH1, and Mangala) were sown during 1st wk of December. The treatments comprised two types of seedbeds (raised and flat) and four seedbed conditions: control; nursery beds covered with rice straw at 5 t/ha; nursery beds covered with transparent polythene sheeting (300 gauge) at 45 cm above ground level, keeping the bed airtight for 15 d after sowing (DAS) and later exposing the seedlings to the natural environment; and a double dose of the

recommended P (88 kg/ha) applied before sowing.

Air temperature at 5 cm above the soil surface outside and under the covering and soil temperature at 5 cm below the surface were recorded every day for 15 DAS (Table 1).

Air and soil temperatures were approximately 20 °C in the control treatment. Covering the nursery beds with polythene sheeting increased seedling dry weight from 0.28 to 1.0 g, presumably as a result of the increased temperature.

In contrast, the lower soil temperature under the rice straw mulch resulted in a decline in seedling dry weight to 0.05 g.

A double dose of P increased seedling dry weight to 0.73 g without any significant change in soil temperature (Table 2). This suggests the most critical factor determining the growth rate of seedlings under low soil temperature conditions may be availability of an immobile nutrient such as P. Seedbed condition, raised or flat beds, nonpuddled or puddled condition, and not impounding or impounding water may also have influenced seedling height to a lesser extent in the double P treatment.

Using either polythene sheeting or applying P could provide 25-d-old seedlings suitable for transplanting in the Hill Zone. ■

Effect of planting date on grain yield and quality of semidwarf scented rice varieties

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With the release of semidwarf scented rice varieties, the optimum planting time had to be determined to exploit their grain yield potential while still maintaining grain quality.

Field experiments were conducted during 1990-91 wet seasons at the DRR experimental farm in Rajendranagar. The

clay (Vertisols) soil has low to medium available N and P with pH 8.2. Semidwarf scented varieties Haryana Basmati 1, Pusa Basmati 1, and Kasturi were tested with check variety Basmati 370 under three planting dates: 15 Jul, 25 Jul, and 4 Aug.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications, with varieties in main plots and planting dates in subplots. A single dose of 22 kg P/ha and 33.2 kg K/ha was applied along with three splits of the recommended N dose of 90 kg/ha: 45 kg as a basal dressing, 22.5 kg at tillering, and 22.5 kg at panicle initiation. Twenty-five-d-old seedlings (2-3/hill) were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing.

All three improved varieties were significantly superior over Basmati 370 during 1991, although differences among them were nonsignificant. Mean yield increase over that of Basmati 370 was 45.0% for Pusa Basmati 1, 42.2 % for Haryana Basmati 1, and 36.3% for Kasturi. A significantly linear reduction in grain yield was recorded with successive delay in planting from 3.8 t/ha from 15 Jul to 2.8 t/ha from 4 Aug. Average grain yield was reduced by 21.1% for 25 Jul planting and 27.8% for 4 Aug compared with the grain yield for 15 Jul planting. Daylight hours were maximum for the crop planted on 25 Jul. The maximum mean day temperature was

Grain yield and quality parameters of semidwarf scented rice varieties under different planting dates. DRR, Rajendranagar, AP, India. 1990-91 WS.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)			Grain quality parameters ^a								
	1990	1991	Mean	Hulling (%)	Milling (%)	Head rice recovery (%)	Kernel length (mm)		Elongation ratio	Alkali value	Amylose value (%) 1991	Aroma
							Before cooking	After cooking				
<i>Variety</i>												
<i>Haryana</i>												
Basmati 1	3.6	3.5	3.6	76.8	71.1	27.3	6.8	11.5	1.7	6.56-6.57	20.3	SS ^b
<i>Pusa</i>												
Basmati 1	3.5	3.8	3.6	75.5	70.6	33.8	6.6	12.4	1.9	5.65-5.67	20.3	SS
Kasturi	3.3	3.5	3.4	75.9	70.1	42.7	6.7	12.0	1.8	5.48-5.51	18.0	SS
Basmati 370	-	2.5	2.5	77.2	72.5	24.7	6.5	11.1	1.7	-	-	SS
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.3										
<i>Planting date</i>												
15 Jul	3.6	4.0	3.8	76.4	71.0	28.8	6.6	11.3	1.7	5.72-5.80	20.5	SS
25 Jul	3.5	3.2	3.3	75.3	70.3	34.1	6.7	12.4	1.9	6.05-6.03	19.2	SS
4 Aug	3.0	2.6	2.8	76.5	70.8	40.8	6.8	12.3	1.8	5.88-5.92	19.4	SS
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.3										

^aMean of 2 yr. ^bSS = strongly scented.